

PHYSIOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE CHILD IN PREPARATION FOR SCHOOLING.

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Abstract: *The physiological development of the child directly affects school performance and is the basis for the formation of psychological and social readiness for school. Physiological readiness for school is determined by the level of development of the main functional systems of the child's body and the state of his health. The assessment of the physiological readiness of children for systematic schooling is carried out by physicians according to certain criteria*

Key words: *Inclusive education, principles of inclusive education, creativity, moral standards, creativity, leading activity, development of the emotional sphere of children.*

Аннотация: *Физиологическое развитие ребенка непосредственно влияет на школьную успеваемость и является основой для формирования психологической и социальной готовности к школе. Физиологическая готовность к школе определяется уровнем развития основных функциональных систем организма ребенка и состоянием его здоровья. Оценку физиологической готовности детей к систематическому школьному обучению проводят медики по определенным критериям*

Ключевые слова: *Инклюзивное обучение, принципы инклюзивного обучения, творческие способности, нравственные нормы, способность к творчеству, ведущий вид деятельности, развитие эмоциональной сферы детей.*

The level of physiological development and the state of health of the child form the foundation of school activities. Often ill, physically weakened students,

even with a high level of development of mental abilities, as a rule, experience learning difficulties.

The medical record of future first graders contains fairly detailed information about the somatic development of the child (weight, height, body proportions, etc. relative to the age norm), while practically nothing is said about the state of the nervous system. Meanwhile, according to St. Petersburg scientists, 40 - 60% of children 6 - 8 years of age during a special examination revealed various types of minimal brain dysfunction (MMD).

From the point of view of mental development, these children correspond to the norm and should be educated in a regular school. Under favorable conditions, functional and minimal organic disorders of the nervous system can be compensated with age. At the same time, children with MMD and neurotics are characterized by some features of behavior and activity that must be taken into account when organizing the educational process: decreased memory and attention functions, increased fatigue, irritability, difficulties in communicating with peers, hyperactivity or slowness, difficulties in accepting educational tasks and reduced self-control. The reasons causing functional and organic deviations in the development of the nervous system can be different: severe pregnancy and complicated childbirth, certain diseases in infancy and early age, head injuries and bruises, stressful situations (fire, flood, death of a loved one, divorce of parents) unfavorable conditions in the family.

With the beginning of schooling, the load on the child's body increases dramatically. Systematic educational work, a large amount of new information, the need to maintain a forced posture for a long time, a change in the usual daily routine. Is the body of a 6-7 year old child ready for such loads? Numerous studies by physiologists indicate that at the age of 5–7 years, a significant restructuring of all the physiological systems of the child's body takes place. By the beginning of schooling (by the age of seven), this restructuring has not yet been completed, and active physiological development continues during the school years. Therefore, scientists conclude: on the one hand, according to its functional characteristics, the

body of a child of 6-7 years old is ready for systematic schooling, at the same time, it is very sensitive to adverse environmental influences, especially to excessive mental and physical stress.

The younger the child, the more difficult it is for him to cope with school workloads, the higher the likelihood of deviations in his health.

It must also be remembered that all children develop differently, the actual age of the child does not always correspond to the biological one: one child at the age of 6 is ready for systematic education in terms of his physical development, and at the age of 7 the usual school load will be beyond his strength.

The results of a study of the morphofunctional and psychophysiological development of children aged 6–10 showed that at the age of six, almost half of the boys and a third of the girls do not reach the level of development necessary for schooling. By the age of seven, the number of physiologically "mature" children significantly increases and the number of "immature" children, especially girls, decreases.

All children entering the 1st grade must undergo a medical examination, on the basis of which a conclusion is made about the functional readiness for schooling. A child is considered ready for schooling if, in terms of physical and biological development, he corresponds to the formal age or is ahead of it and has no medical contraindications.

Criteria for the physiological readiness of children to study at school:

1. The level of physical development.
2. The level of biological development.
3. State of health.

When determining physical development, three main indicators are usually assessed: body length (height, standing and sitting), body weight and chest circumference.

Older preschoolers grow very quickly, adding 7-10 cm in height per year. It is no coincidence that this age is called the period of "stretching in length". The increase in body weight is 2.2-2.5 kg annually, the circumference of the chest increases by 2.0-2.5 cm. At this age, physical development in girls proceeds more intensively

than in boys. The jump in physical development at the age of 6-7 is due to neuroendocrine changes in the child's body. Doctors consider this period to be critical, they note a decrease in physical and mental endurance and an increase in the risk of diseases.

The criteria for biological age are the number of erupted permanent teeth, the achievement of certain proportions.

boys

Number of permanent teeth

5 years - 0-1

5.5 years - 0-3

6 years - 1-4

6.5 years - 2-8

7 years - 6-10

Ratio of head circumference to body length

5 years - 49.4-45.0

5.5 years - 47.9-44.3

6 years - 46.6-43.1

6.5 years - 45.4-41.9

7 years - 44.7-41.3

The ratio of head circumference and body length becomes almost the same as in an adult. In addition, the length of the arms and legs increases.

In the existing scheme for a comprehensive assessment of the state of health, all children are divided into five groups.

The first group - children without any functional abnormalities with good physical development, rarely sick. The number of such children entering the first grade of a mass school does not exceed 20-25%.

The second group - children with some functional disorders, who are on the verge of health and disease, which has not yet become a chronic process. Under unfavorable conditions, they may develop more pronounced and persistent deviations in health status. Muscle development is facilitated by precise, finely

coordinated movements of the fingers: modeling clay, tightening nuts in a children's designer, picking up patterns from small mosaics, embroidery, tying knots, fastening small buttons. You can use games with small balls, such that you can hold with one hand.

A variety of "finger games" and gymnastics for fingers are very useful and arouse interest in children.

To prepare a child for school, it is necessary to develop not only those parts of the musculoskeletal system that provide graphic activity and written exercises. Movement is the main condition for the normal growth and development of the body. The results of a medical examination show that sedentary, passive children lag behind their peers in development, often get sick, and study poorly. Movements not only strengthen the musculoskeletal system, develop motor skills and coordination, they ensure the continuous synthesis of protein compounds in the muscles and contribute to their normal growth. At preschool age, it is necessary to develop and maintain in children the need for movement, to form the skills of walking, running, climbing, throwing, swimming.

List of used literature:

1. Абрамова, Г.С. Возрастная психология: Учебное пособие для студентов вузов. - М.: Академический проект; Екатеринбург: Деловая книга, 2008.
2. Волков, Б.С. Психология младшего школьника: учебное пособие. - М.: Академический Проект: Альма Мастер, 2006. - 321 с.
3. Выготский, Л.С. Психология. - М.: ЭКСМО-Пресс, 2008. - 1008 с.
4. Выготский, Л.С. Мышление речи. - М.: Педагогика, 2007. - 432 с.
5. Урунтаева, Г.А. Дошкольная психология: Учебное пособие. / Г.А. Урунтаева. - М.: Academ A. - 1997. -236 с.
1. Muhammadjanovna, Rakhimova Feruzakhon. "THE SYSTEM OF FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE ACTIVITY OF FUTURE EDUCATORS THROUGH PERSONCENTERED EDUCATION." World Bulletin of Social Sciences 7 (2022): 75-77.

2. Mirzaeva, Farokhat, et al. "IMPROVING THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS BASED ON A PEDAGOGICAL INNOVATIVE APPROACH." *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology* 17.6 (2020): 8919-8926.
3. Muhammadjonovna, Rakhimova Feruzakhon. "Improvement Of The System Of Formation And Development Of Creative Activity Of Future Educators On The Basis Of PersonalityOriented Education." *Eurasian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences* 3 (2021): 32-36.
4. Mukhammadjonovna, Rakhimova Feruzakhon. "Pedagogical and psychological features of the formation of the creative activity of future teachers through personality-oriented education." *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal* 11.4 (2021): 1053-1056.
5. Raximova, Feruzaxon Muxammadjonovna. "PROBLEMS OF ESTABLISHING AND STRENGTHENING THE MATERIAL BASE OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION ORGANIZATION." *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире* 4-7 (2021): 51-56.
5. Akilovna, Esonova Maloxat. "METHODS OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGUES." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.05 (2022): 228-232.
6. Akilovna, Esonova Malohat, and Boymirzayeva Fotima. "MODERN APPROACHES TO CHILDREN'S INTELLECTUAL DEVELOPMENT." *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429 11.05 (2022): 233-237.
7. Nazirova, Guzal, Dilfuza Yulchiboeva, and Oxunjon Khaydarov. "The Main Factors of Formation and Development of Professional Competence of Teachers of Preschool Educational Organizations." *REVISTA GEINTEC-GESTAO INOVACAO E TECNOLOGIAS* 11.3 (2021): 1698-1708.
8. Nazirova, Guzal M. "Features of Organization Pedagogical Process in Preschool Educational Institutions." *Eastern European Scientific Journal* 1 (2017).

9. Djuraev, R. X., S. T. Turgunov, and G. M. Nazirova. "Pedagogy." T.: O'zPFITI (2013).

10. Назирова, Г. М. "РАЗВИТИЕ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ КОМПЕТЕНТНОСТИ ВОСПИТАТЕЛЕЙ ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЙ НА ОСНОВЕ СИСТЕМНОГО ПОДХОДА." Актуальные проблемы современной науки 4 (2014): 96-99.

11. Назирова, Г. М. "Особенности процесса деятельности воспитателей дошкольных образовательных учреждений." Вопросы гуманитарных наук 4 (2014): 61-63.